

Kinetic-spectrophotometric determination of trace amounts of bromide based on its catalytic effect on methyl red-bromate reaction

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Abstract : A simple, sensitive and rapid method has been developed for kinetic spectrophotometric determination of trace amounts of bromide. The method is based on the catalytic effect of bromide on the oxidation reaction of methyl red by potassium bromate in the presence of hydrochloric acid. The reaction is followed spectrophotometrically by measuring the change in absorbance (ΔA) at 517 nm using a fixed time method (6 min). The method allows the determination of bromide in the range of 50–1200 ng ml⁻¹. The proposed method was successfully applied to the determination of bromide in water samples.

Keywords : Bromide, methyl red, bromate.

Determination of bromide is important in a variety of samples such as natural waters, food and biological fluids. Several analytical techniques such as GC-mass¹, ion chromatography², high performance liquid chromatography³, capillary electrophoresis⁴ and inductively coupled plasma emission spectrophotometry⁵ have proposed and used for the determination of bromide. Some of these techniques are time consuming and require expensive and sophisticated instruments. Kinetic spectrophotometric methods have been recognized as offering a valuable approach to trace analysis because of high sensitivity, sufficient accuracy and necessity of less expensive instruments. Many kinetic-catalytic methods have been proposed for the determination of bromide based on different indicator reactions^{6,7}.

In this paper we wish to report a sensitive kinetic spectrophotometric method for the determination of trace amounts of bromide based on its catalytic effect on oxidation reaction of methyl red by bromate in acidic media.

Experimental

Absorption spectra were recorded on a Jasco model 7850 UV-Visible spectrophotometer with a 1 cm glass cell and all absorption measurements were made using a Perkin-Elmer model 550S spectrophotometer. A Colora C-1668 thermostat was used for controlling the temperature within ± 1 °C.

Analytical-reagent grade chemicals and double dis-

tilled water were used throughout the experiment. A 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ stock solution of bromide was prepared by dissolving 0.2570 g of sodium bromide (Merck) in water and diluting to 1000 ml in volumetric flask. Further dilutions were made daily. A 0.01 mol L⁻¹ methyl red solution was prepared by dissolving 0.5388 g of methyl red in 8 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid and diluting to 200 ml in a volumetric flask. A 2×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ solution of methyl red was then prepared by appropriate dilution of this solution. A solution of 0.01 mol L⁻¹ bromate was prepared by dissolving 0.1509 g of sodium bromate (Merck) in water and diluting to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask. A solution of hydrochloric acid (1 mol L⁻¹) was prepared by appropriate dilution of concentrated acid (Merck).

An appropriate amount of standard bromide solution was transferred into a 10 ml flask so that the final concentration would be in the range of 50–1200 ng ml⁻¹. Then 1.5 ml of 2×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ solution of methyl red, 2 ml of 1 mol L⁻¹ solution of hydrochloric acid and enough water for diluting the solution to ca. 7 ml, were added and 2.5 ml of 2.5×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹ solution of sodium bromate was added and diluted exactly to the mark. The zero time was taken as the moment at which the last drop of bromate solution has been added. A portion of the solution was transferred into a glass cell the absorbance was measured after 6 min. A blank solution was also prepared in the same way using distilled water instead of

bromide. All the solutions were placed in a thermostat at 23 ± 0.1 °C before use.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectrum of methyl red shows that maximum absorption occurs at 517 nm. This reagent is oxidized by bromate in hydrochloric acid and its absorbance decreases. The presence of bromide accelerates the reaction and the rate of reaction increases with increasing bromide concentration. The reaction of bromate and chloride ions in acidic media produces Cl_2 and Br_2 according to the following equation :

The produced Cl_2 and Br_2 could react with methyl red and decolorize it⁸.

The catalytic effect of bromide on the reaction of methyl red with bromate was used for the determination of bromide by monitoring the absorbance with time at 517 nm.

In order to optimize the variables, the effect of concentration of each reagent on the rate of reaction was studied. Maximum change in absorbance was obtained when methyl red concentration was 3.0×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹ in the final solution. Therefore 1.5 ml of 2.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ methyl red was added to the 10 ml solution to achieve this concentration in the final solution. The influence of bromate ion concentration on the reaction rate was also studied. The results showed that by increasing the bromate concentration, the rate of reaction was increased up to a concentration of 6.2×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ in the final solution and above that it was decreased again. This concentration was chosen for further work.

The effect of acidity on the reaction was investigated. The highest change in absorbance occurred when acid concentration was 0.2 mol L⁻¹ in the final solution and this concentration was chosen for all measurements. Increasing the temperature increased the analytical sensitivity of the catalyzed reaction, but 23 ± 0.1 °C was chosen for convenience.

The change in absorbance (ΔA) against bromide concentration was linear in the range of 50–1200 ng ml⁻¹ of bromide. The equation of the line was $\Delta A = -0.019 + 4.7 \times 10^{-4} C_M$, where C_M is bromide concentration in ng ml⁻¹ and correlation coefficient was 0.9995. The detection limit based on $3S_b$ was 15.5 ng ml⁻¹ and the rela-

tive standard deviation (RSD) for eight replicate measurements of 500 and 1200 ng ml⁻¹ of bromide was 1.55 and 0.45%, respectively.

The interference effects of various cations and anions on the reaction were studied for 500 ng ml⁻¹ of bromide. A relative error of 5% was considered tolerable. The tolerance ratio for the ions studied are as : K^+ , Na^+ , Cr^{3+} , NO_3^- , SO_3^{2-} 1000; Cd^{2+} , PO_4^{3-} , acetate 500; Al^{3+} , CN^- 300; Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , NH_4^+ , CO_3^{2-} , Mg^{2+} 100; Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} 50; I^- 10.

The proposed method was applied to the determination of bromide in tap water. The results are reproducible to $\pm 2.0\%$.

Conclusions :

A simple and sensitive method with good selectivity is proposed for the determination of bromide in the range of 50–1200 ng ml⁻¹ using its catalytic effect on methyl red-bromate reaction. The proposed method can be applied to the analysis of bromide in water samples with good precision and accuracy. The method also offers a higher sensitivity comparing to some of the similar previously reported catalytic method⁷.

References

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